

1 **REVIEW ARTICLE**

2 **Beyond Bacilli: Integrating the Microbiome into the TB Research Agenda**

3 Edson Mambuque^{1,2*}, Ana del Amo-de Palacios^{3*}, Samuel G. Huete³, Charissa C. Marsh^{4,5},
4 Grant Theron⁴, Alberto L. García-Basteiro^{1,2}, Sergio Serrano-Villar^{3,6}

5 **Affiliations**

- 6 1. Centro de Investigação em Saúde de Manhiça (CISM). Maputo, Mozambique
- 7 2. Barcelona Institute for Global Health (ISGlobal). Hospital Clinic, Universitat de
8 Barcelona. CIBERINFEC, Barcelona, Spain.
- 9 3. Department of Infectious Diseases, Hospital Ramón y Cajal, IRYCIS, CIBERINFEC,
10 Madrid, Spain.
- 11 4. DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence for Biomedical Tuberculosis Research, SAMRC Centre
12 for Molecular and Cellular Biology, Division of Molecular Biology and Human Genetics,
13 Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Stellenbosch University, Cape Town, South
14 Africa.
- 15
- 16 5. African Microbiome Institute, Division of Molecular Biology and Human Genetics,
17 Department of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences,
18 Stellenbosch University, Cape Town, South Africa
19
- 20 6. Life Science Campus. Universidad Antonio de Nebrija, Madrid, Spain.
- 21

22 *Co-first authors

23 **Correspondence:** Sergio Serrano-Villar. Department of Infectious Diseases. Ctra. Colmenar
24 Viejo, km 9.100. 28034 Madrid, Spain. Email: sergio.serrano@salud.madrid.org.

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26

27 **Abstract**

28 Tuberculosis (TB) remains a leading infectious killer, with growing evidence that the human
29 microbiome—particularly in the gut and lungs—shapes susceptibility, progression, and treatment
30 outcomes. Over the past decade, studies have reported TB-associated dysbiosis, more
31 consistently in the gut than in the lung, often marked by loss of short-chain fatty acid–producing
32 taxa and expansion of opportunistic microbes. However, findings are frequently confounded by
33 diet, antibiotic exposure, co-morbidities, geography, and methodological variability. Most research
34 has relied on compositional profiling, offering limited insight into functional mechanisms. This
35 narrative review synthesizes recent evidence, emphasizing the need to integrate multi-omics
36 approaches—metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, metabolomics—and experimental validation
37 to uncover causal links between microbiome alterations and TB pathogenesis or therapy
38 response. We discuss potential clinical applications, including microbiome-based diagnostics
39 (such as stool-based microbial or metabolite signatures for TB risk stratification), prognostic
40 indicators (like gut microbiome recovery predicting immune normalization during therapy), and
41 adjunctive interventions (including microbiome-derived products to reduce drug-induced liver
42 injury or fecal microbiota transplantation, which has been shown safe in people with HIV on stable
43 ART) to mitigate drug toxicity or enhance immune recovery. Key priorities include methodological
44 standardization, confounder control, mechanistic studies, and inclusion of high-burden settings.
45 By moving beyond descriptive surveys toward functional, translational research, integrating
46 insights from different microbiome methods into TB prevention, diagnosis, and treatment could
47 redefine the clinical research agenda and open new avenues for precision medicine in this global
48 disease.

49 **Keywords:** microbiome, tuberculosis, methodological standardization, confounder control,
50 mechanistic studies.

51

52

53 Introduction

54 Tuberculosis (TB), caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb), remains a major global killer (1).
55 Beyond the lungs, the respiratory and gut microbiomes may influence TB risk, progression, and
56 treatment outcomes (2). Yet, major gaps remain in understanding the risk factors driving
57 progression and treatment outcomes, highlighting the importance of investigating additional host
58 and external modulators—such as concomitant infections (e.g., CMV) and the microbiome—to
59 inform personalized TB control strategies. Although factors like undernutrition, HIV, and diabetes
60 have stronger effects on TB outcomes, emerging evidence suggests microbiome shifts—though
61 likely smaller in magnitude—can still influence immunity and drug response. Studies suggest that
62 TB and its therapy perturb these communities, while microbiome composition and function can
63 modulate host immunity (3). Interest in a “gut–lung axis” is growing, though interpretation is
64 complicated by confounders such as diet, co-morbidities, and sampling methods (2,4). Most
65 research has used 16S rRNA surveys, which reveal composition but not function; distinct
66 communities may share capacities, and functional shifts may drive clinical effects (5,6).

67 The TB field is shifting from cataloguing microbial taxa to decoding the functional and clinical
68 relevance of host–microbiome interactions. This narrative review synthesizes emerging evidence,
69 addresses critical methodological pitfalls, and proposes a translational roadmap for integrating
70 microbiome insights into TB care. Unlike previous reviews focused largely on taxonomic surveys,
71 this piece critically integrates recent evidence on key confounders, functional multi-omics
72 analyses, and clinical applications, outlining a translational framework to embed the microbiome
73 into the TB diagnostic and therapeutic agenda. We highlight major confounding variables that
74 must be addressed for reproducible results, discuss differences between pulmonary and intestinal
75 microbiomes in TB, and argue for multi-omics approaches that move beyond simple
76 compositional analysis.

77 Importantly, we advocate that major TB drug and vaccine trials routinely incorporate a microbiome
78 readout—or at least biobanking of appropriate samples—as these large-scale, resource-intensive
79 studies offer a unique opportunity to generate high-quality, clinically relevant microbiome data
80 without duplicating effort. We also explore potential clinical applications of microbiome data in TB
81 –from biomarkers of disease or treatment response to adjuvant therapies– and outline key
82 challenges, knowledge gaps, and future research directions needed to translate microbiome
83 insights into improved TB care.

84 Overview of Microbiome Research in TB

85 TB–microbiome research has grown rapidly, examining both lung and gut communities.
86 Pulmonary findings, often from sputum as a proxy, are inconsistent: some report no diversity
87 differences (7), others note increased *Streptococcus* or *Haemophilus* in TB (8). A key contributor
88 to this inconsistency is the use of sputum, which is a heterogeneous mixture of upper and lower
89 airway microbiota. A multicenter study found no universal lung signature, with variation driven by
90 geography and individuals (9). Gut studies are more consistent: TB has been associated with
91 depletion of beneficial short-chain fatty acid (SCFA) producers (such as certain Clostridiales) ,
92 and enrichment of opportunistic pro-inflammatory taxa such as *Enterobacteriaceae*,

93 *Streptococcus*, and *Enterococcus* (4). In one cohort, healthy household contacts had more
94 *Prevotella* and *Bifidobacterium*, whereas people with TB had more butyrate-producers like
95 *Faecalibacterium* and *Roseburia* (5). Shotgun metagenomic analyses revealed a reduced genetic
96 capacity for vitamin and amino acid biosynthesis and an increased abundance of genes involved
97 in short-chain fatty acid (SCFA) pathways, supporting the hypothesis—yet to be functionally
98 validated—that TB-associated dysbiosis may promote an anti-inflammatory milieu affecting host
99 immunity (5). However, even in gut studies, the magnitude and direction of specific taxa-level
100 associations can vary with undernutrition, HIV/diabetes comorbidity, antecedent antibiotics, and
101 local diet—factors that are unevenly measured and adjusted across cohorts.

102 Anti-TB therapy itself is a major disruptor of the microbiome. Standard regimens rapidly alter gut
103 communities, with marked loss of SCFA-producing *Firmicutes* and expansion of *Bacteroides*
104 within 1–2 weeks (10). One longitudinal study showed that while active TB itself led to only a
105 minor decrease in gut α -diversity, initiating treatment caused a profound dysbiosis with >50% of
106 gut bacterial taxa changing in relative abundance (11), while others find minimal change (9),
107 highlighting contextual and methodological influences. However, the majority of human studies
108 focus on short-term changes during the intensive phase of therapy, with follow-up often limited to
109 weeks or a few months, limiting inference about microbiome recovery or persistence beyond early
110 treatment.

111 Overall, TB and its treatment seems to disrupt both gut and airway microbiota, but patterns vary
112 by study and population. Across studies, many reported pulmonary associations attenuate after
113 accounting for key confounders (including geography, HIV status, sampling approach, and
114 contamination control), contributing to limited reproducibility of ‘universal’ lung signatures.
115 Consequently, pulmonary microbiome signals in TB should be interpreted primarily as context-
116 dependent until validated in well-controlled, multi-site cohorts. Recent work is testing whether
117 these shifts influence outcomes, with evidence from human, animal, and Mendelian
118 randomization studies suggesting gut microbiota composition can affect TB risk—protective taxa
119 like *Bacillales* and risk-associated *Bacteroidaceae* have been identified (12). These insights are
120 driving interest in microbiome-targeted TB prevention and therapy, despite remaining challenges
121 and confounders. An overview of the current evidence, highlighting areas of convergence and
122 heterogeneity across pulmonary and intestinal studies, together with the major design and
123 methodological drivers of divergence, is summarized in [Tables 1](#) and [2](#).

124

125 **Major Confounding Factors in TB-Microbiome Studies**

126 Low microbial biomass in lung samples represents one of the most critical and underappreciated
127 sources of bias in TB microbiome research. Low agreement among studies exploring the
128 microbiota’s role in human disease remains a major barrier to establishing causal relationships
129 between host-associated microbes and pathology. These discrepancies often arise from
130 uncontrolled **confounding factors** that influence microbiota composition independently of
131 disease status (13). Key confounding factors in TB-microbiome studies include patient-specific
132 variables (e.g. diet, co-infections and co-morbidities, medications), environmental and

133 sociocultural factors, and technical and methodological variables. **Table 1** and **Figure 1**
134 summarize major confounders and their relevance. **Figure 2** illustrates these factors using
135 directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) to highlight how different domains—patient, environmental, and
136 methodological—may introduce bias in observed microbiome–TB associations. Not all of these
137 have been conclusively demonstrated as confounders in TB cohorts, but they are plausible
138 sources of variability given evidence from other conditions and some emerging TB-specific
139 studies. Moreover, certain “confounders” such as poor diet or HIV co-infection are themselves
140 strong causal risk factors for TB; in these cases, microbiome changes may reflect relevant host-
141 pathogen interactions rather than noise.

142 For diagnostic applications, associations between microbiome features and TB may still be
143 clinically useful even if causality is complex. In contrast, mechanistic inference requires explicit
144 control of confounding. Notably, only a limited subset of reported TB–microbiome associations
145 have been shown to persist after accounting for major covariates (e.g., pathogen
146 burden/clearance, HIV status, and geography), whereas many pulmonary signatures remain
147 inconsistent across settings (**Table 2**). While complete control is rarely feasible in human cohorts
148 given the diversity of TB presentations and populations, strategies such as careful case–control
149 matching, stratified analyses, multivariable adjustment, and replication across independent
150 cohorts can help mitigate bias and strengthen the robustness of findings (14).

151 ***Patient diet and nutritional status***

152 Nutritional status profoundly shapes the gut microbiome and immune function (15–17). TB often
153 afflicts populations with high rates of undernutrition and food insecurity. Malnutrition itself is a
154 known risk factor for active TB progression and is associated with microbiome alterations (such
155 as loss of fiber-degrading commensals) that could confound comparisons (18). Dietary patterns
156 differ across regions and between cases/controls; for example, a study in West Africa noted that
157 healthy controls from different households displayed substantial microbiome variation due to
158 differences in diet and socioeconomic status, limiting their utility as a single reference group (4).
159 However, even when household contacts are used, studies rarely account for shared exposures
160 or subclinical immune alterations related to recent *M. tuberculosis* contact, underscoring the need
161 to interpret comparator-dependent microbiome differences with caution. Ideally, controls should
162 be well-matched for diet and nutritional status, or analyses should adjust for body mass index and
163 diet-related metadata (19). Some studies use household contacts of people with TB as controls
164 to minimize differences in diet and environment (4), while others have argued that “sick controls”
165 with non-TB lung disease may in some contexts provide a more appropriate comparison group.
166

167 ***Antibiotic exposures (including TB medications)***

168 Antibiotic use is a potent modulator of microbiome composition. Many people with TB have a
169 history of broad-spectrum antibiotic use (for other infections or misdiagnosis) or are started on
170 empiric antibiotics when TB is suspected, which can significantly alter microbiota before sampling
171 (2). More obviously, all people with TB receive prolonged multi-drug therapy —most commonly
172 the standard first-line regimen comprising isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol

173 (HRZE)— which itself causes microbiome disruption (10). If microbiome samples are taken during
174 or after treatment, it becomes difficult to disentangle effects of the infection from effects of the
175 drugs. For example, one study found that several gut bacterial genera decreased sharply within
176 a week of TB treatment initiation, consistent with a rapid loss of susceptible commensals after
177 HRZE exposure (10). If microbiome samples are collected during or after treatment, it becomes
178 difficult to disentangle effects of the infection from effects of the drugs. Without proper control,
179 one might incorrectly attribute this loss to TB disease when it was drug-induced.

180
181 Importantly, the nature and extent of microbiome perturbation vary not only with the timing of
182 sampling but also with regimen composition and treatment duration, as different drug
183 combinations exert distinct ecological pressures. The relative contribution of individual drugs
184 remains incompletely defined; however, rifampicin's broad antibacterial activity beyond
185 *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* makes it a biologically plausible contributor to treatment-associated
186 dysbiosis. At a mechanistic level, these alterations are thought to arise through direct suppression
187 of susceptible commensal taxa, followed by ecological niche expansion of intrinsically resistant
188 or tolerant organisms, with additional indirect host-mediated effects. In the respiratory tract, where
189 baseline microbial biomass is low, even antibiotics not primarily targeting Mtb (e.g.,
190 fluoroquinolones or macrolides) can markedly reduce diversity. A 2019 Lancet review emphasized
191 that TB is typically treated with prolonged antibiotics and microbiome composition is often
192 measured at sites of low microbial biomass, meaning many detected microbiome shifts could be
193 drug effects or contamination (20). Importantly, microbiome disruption is not limited to broad-
194 spectrum drugs: even agents considered narrow-spectrum for *M. tuberculosis*, such as isoniazid,
195 have been associated with gut microbial changes, suggesting off-target or indirect mechanisms
196 that remain poorly understood (21).

197
198 ***Co-infections and co-morbidities***

199 TB frequently co-occurs with other diseases that impact the microbiome. Notably, HIV co-infection
200 is common in TB and causes immunodeficiency that can alter microbiota composition (and
201 increase infection by normally latent microbes). In one study, sputum from TB/HIV co-infected
202 patients had a higher prevalence of certain viruses (e.g. EBV, anellovirus) dominating the
203 microbiome (22), presumably reflecting HIV-related immune changes rather than TB. HIV, by
204 itself, has been linked to dysbiosis of the gut (23,24) and lung microbiome (25), so comparing
205 HIV-positive TB cases to HIV-negative controls would be confounded.

206 Helminth infections (and other gut parasitoses) are also highly prevalent in TB-endemic settings
207 and can reshape the gut microbiome while skewing host immunity toward Th2/Treg phenotypes
208 (26); these effects may modulate TB susceptibility and responses and have even been argued
209 to influence BCG effectiveness (27).

210 Diabetes mellitus is another major TB risk factor; diabetic patients often have a distinct gut
211 microbiome (e.g. lower butyrate producers, higher opportunists) even without TB. A 2023 study
212 explicitly examined people with TB with and without diabetes and found that TB was associated
213 with gut dysbiosis, but the TB-DM subgroup had additional alterations, notably increased

214 *Bacteroides* and *Blautia* (4). However, it remains unclear whether these differences are driven by
215 diabetes itself, TB, or their combined effects, underscoring the challenge of attributing microbiome
216 shifts to a single condition in co-morbid populations.

217
218 Other co-morbidities to consider include chronic liver disease, smoking-related lung disease, and
219 helminth or other chronic infections endemic in some TB populations. Co-infections and host
220 variables such as parasitic infections have been shown to substantially influence gut microbiome
221 composition and host immune tone, and to act as major confounders in human microbiome–
222 disease association studies, particularly in low- and middle-income settings (13). Helminth
223 infections, in particular, can substantially reshape the gut microbiome and skew host immunity
224 toward regulatory or Th2-biased responses, with potential implications for TB susceptibility and
225 immune responses (26,27). Accordingly, future studies should collect helminth
226 exposure/treatment data (e.g., stool antigen/PCR, deworming status), or at least store sufficient
227 specimens for retrospective testing, and consider stratification by helminth infection, alongside
228 careful matching on HIV and diabetes, or inclusion of these variables in multivariable models, to
229 reduce bias and clarify microbiome–TB relationships (13, 14).

230

231 ***Geography and environment***

232 The microbiome varies significantly by geography, climate, and lifestyle (urban vs. rural, etc.).
233 People with TB in different regions may have different baseline microbiomes simply due to their
234 environment and culture, not the disease. A multicenter study analysis sputum samples found
235 location-specific signatures, with no universal pattern across sites; a microbial signature seen in
236 Bangladesh was not seen in Switzerland, for example (9). While using household or community
237 controls and adjusting for geography can help control for confounding, well-designed multi-site
238 studies with standardized protocols and matched controls can also enhance generalizability and
239 help identify microbiome signatures applicable across diverse settings.

240

241 Socioeconomic factors (sanitation, crowding, diet diversity) also confound microbiome findings.
242 One approach is to use household or community controls who share the environment with TB
243 cases (4). Another is to include geography as a covariate in analysis or focus within a single
244 homogeneous population to reduce environmental variation. Seasonality can even play a role. In
245 a multi-omics study in 105 individuals over four years in California, the human nasal and gut
246 microbiomes exhibited significant seasonal variation, with greater shifts observed in nasal taxa,
247 and specific gut microbes such as *Holdemania*, *Oscillibacter*, and *Firmicutes* (28). That said, in
248 TB-specific cohorts, the effect of seasonality on microbiome composition appeared relatively
249 small compared with other drivers such as geography, host comorbidities, or antibiotic exposure—
250 though TB incidence itself also shows seasonal variation, which may complicate interpretation
251 (29). Accordingly, if samples from people with TB were collected in a different season than
252 controls, seasonal diet changes could alter gut microbiota.

253 **Sampling site and method**

254 How and from where samples are obtained is a critical methodological factor. This is especially
255 pertinent for the lung microbiome. TB lung disease often requires sputum expectoration for
256 microbiological diagnosis; however, sputum is a mix of lower airway secretions and upper airway
257 flora (from the oropharynx) picked up during expectoration. Healthy controls generally do not
258 produce sputum, so studies sometimes use throat swabs or oral wash samples for controls. If not
259 carefully considered, this mismatch can confound results – differences might stem from sample
260 type rather than TB status. A pilot study in patients with TB and controls comparing nasal swabs,
261 throat swabs, and sputum found that oropharyngeal (throat) communities resembled those in
262 sputum, proposing oropharyngeal communities as a surrogate for control sampling (30) .
263 Nonetheless, subtle differences existed. Thus, intra-study consistency in sampling is key: some
264 studies collect oropharyngeal swabs from both people with TB (in addition to sputum) and controls
265 to allow direct comparison (30).

266
267 Invasive sampling like bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) yields a more direct lower airway sample but
268 is rarely feasible in healthy controls and can itself introduce organisms or select for certain
269 communities (hospital environment, bronchoscope contamination). For gut microbiome, stool is
270 the standard sample; differences in stool collection/handling (immediate freezing vs. delay, etc.)
271 can introduce variability but this is mostly offset by its high biomass and sampling protocols are
272 easier to standardize (20,31).

273 **Laboratory and analytical methods**

274 Microbiome results can be profoundly affected by DNA extraction protocols, sequencing primers,
275 and bioinformatics pipelines. While standard microbiome considerations (e.g., batch/run effects)
276 should be controlled and corrected, our focus is on TB-specific sources of variation that can
277 masquerade as disease signals. Sputum or BAL are particularly prone to contamination from DNA
278 extraction kits or reagents (the so-called “kitome”) (20). Sputum generally contains higher
279 microbial biomass than BALF and is therefore somewhat less vulnerable to reagent
280 contamination, but it is instead confounded by oral carryover during expectoration. For example,
281 reagent contamination might introduce *Ralstonia* or *Pelomonas* DNA that could be misinterpreted
282 as part of the lung microbiome if appropriate controls (blank extractions) are not included.
283 Furthermore, ‘background’ DNA from medical apparatus used during bronchoscopy need to be
284 accounted for (i.e., including bronchoscope wash controls during DNA extractions). Distinguishing
285 true lung residents from contaminants is a known challenge in pulmonary microbiome studies
286 (20). Furthermore, different 16S rRNA gene primers have varying coverage of key taxa; may
287 under-detect important anaerobes, leading to bias (32).

288 Without these controls, apparent enrichment of specific taxa in TB lung samples may reflect
289 contamination rather than true biological differences, contributing to the lack of reproducible
290 pulmonary microbiome signatures across studies.

291 **Study design**

292 Careful cohort design is essential for disentangling disease-specific microbiome changes from
293 confounding influences. Sampling patients before treatment and tracking longitudinal changes
294 can offer more meaningful comparisons. Because nearly half of individuals with Mtb infection
295 remain asymptomatic, it is critical to distinguish between latent infection, subclinical TB, and
296 clinically manifest disease when selecting study populations. The type and stage of disease (e.g.,
297 pulmonary vs. extrapulmonary, drug-susceptible vs. drug-resistant) may also strongly influence
298 microbiome composition. In particular, rifampicin-resistant (RR-TB) and multidrug-resistant TB
299 (MDR-TB), which require prolonged treatment with second-line regimens including
300 fluoroquinolones and agents such as bedaquiline, are likely to exert greater and more persistent
301 microbiome disruption than drug-susceptible TB, although direct comparative data across
302 resistance categories remain limited.

303
304 An often-underappreciated source of heterogeneity across TB–microbiome studies is the choice
305 of comparator group. Studies have variably used healthy community controls, household contacts
306 of people with TB, or ‘sick controls’ with non-TB lung disease, each introducing distinct interpretive
307 trade-offs. Healthy community controls are frequently mismatched for diet, socioeconomic status,
308 and environmental exposures, potentially exaggerating apparent dysbiosis. Household contacts
309 provide improved environmental and nutritional matching but may share *M. tuberculosis* exposure
310 or early immune perturbations that complicate attribution to active disease. Conversely, sick
311 controls may help isolate TB-specific effects but introduce alternative inflammatory states or
312 treatment-related confounding. Failure to explicitly align control selection with the underlying
313 research question likely contributes to inconsistent findings and represents a key gap in the
314 current literature. The choice of study population should be guided by the research question: for
315 example, healthy community controls or household contacts are appropriate when studying
316 microbiome correlates of Mtb infection risk; individuals with latent infection provide a comparator
317 for progression studies; and in active disease, the type of TB (e.g., pulmonary vs. extrapulmonary,
318 drug-susceptible vs. MDR) may itself strongly shape the gut or lung microbiome. Standardizing
319 the definition of patient populations across studies is therefore essential. A more informative
320 approach is to compare People with TB with individuals matched on global performance,
321 nutritional status, weight, and other relevant health metrics. Examples of appropriate cases and
322 controls include: (i) People with TB vs. household contacts for transmission and risk studies; (ii)
323 People with TB with vs. without co-morbidities (e.g., HIV, diabetes) for comorbidity effects; and
324 (iii) People with TB pre- vs. post-treatment for therapy-related changes. Matching cases and
325 controls on key variables—such as age, sex, geographic location, diet, and HIV status—enhances
326 comparability and should be prioritized whenever possible (19).

327
328 Longitudinal sampling before, during, and after TB treatment is particularly powerful for
329 distinguishing disease effects from treatment-related changes within the same individual (10).
330 Statistical methods, including multivariable modeling and stratification, can adjust for known
331 confounders like antibiotic use or diabetes, and many of these biostatistical models are now
332 integrated into bioinformatic tools tailored for microbiome analyses, a rapidly evolving field.
333 Examples include ANCOM-BC for differential abundance (33), and integrative multi-omics

334 frameworks such as mixOmics/DIABLO for linking microbiome profiles with host and metabolite
335 data (34). However, the field is still evolving in its ability to model complex longitudinal, multi-omic
336 datasets—particularly those with irregular sampling or small cohort sizes. Residual confounding
337 from unmeasured factors remains a challenge. Findings must therefore be interpreted with
338 caution and ideally validated in independent cohorts. Integrating variables such as nutritional
339 status, co-infections, and host genetics into TB microbiome studies will substantially improve the
340 biological inferences that can be drawn (14). Causal inference methods like Mendelian
341 randomization offer further tools to assess directionality in microbiome–TB associations, and
342 harmonized reporting standards (e.g., STORMS) (35), along with replication across diverse
343 populations, are essential for building a robust and generalizable evidence base.
344

345 **Pulmonary vs. Intestinal Microbiome in TB**

346 TB impacts two key anatomical microbiomes – the pulmonary microbiome at the site of infection,
347 and the intestinal microbiome which influences systemic immunity. These compartments differ
348 markedly in their microbial communities under normal conditions, and TB appears to perturb them
349 in distinct ways. The impact of TB on the microbiome is further shaped by disease phenotype,
350 including pulmonary versus extrapulmonary involvement and drug-susceptible versus drug-
351 resistant forms, although the available evidence is uneven across these categories. Most human
352 microbiome data derive from pulmonary, drug-susceptible TB treated with standard first-line
353 regimens, whereas extrapulmonary TB and drug-resistant TB remain underrepresented. Limited
354 site-of-disease studies in extrapulmonary TB (e.g., lymph node or pericardial TB) suggest distinct
355 local microbial and immunological environments, but these findings are not directly comparable
356 to sputum- or stool-based microbiome analyses.
357

358 With respect to drug resistance, expected differences in microbiome perturbation—particularly in
359 the gut—are largely inferred from prolonged exposure to second-line therapies rather than from
360 direct comparative microbiome data, which remain scarce across resistance categories (RR-, HR-
361 , MDR-, XDR-TB). This imbalance highlights an important gap for future studies integrating
362 disease phenotype, treatment regimen, and anatomical compartment.
363

364 **Table 2** provides a summary of the main findings reported in each compartment.
365

366 The **pulmonary microbiome** in healthy individuals is a low-biomass community with relatively
367 low diversity, often resembling dispersed oral flora, which increases susceptibility to
368 contamination and further constrains confident biological interpretation. In TB, the lung
369 environment undergoes inflammation, tissue damage (cavities), and antibiotic exposure – all of
370 which can alter and be mediated by microbial inhabitants. However, studies of the TB lung
371 microbiome have reported heterogeneous results. This variability points to the need for a formal
372 systematic review and individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis of published studies to
373 harmonize methodologies, account for confounders, and identify reproducible lung microbiome
374 signals in TB.
375

376 Importantly, most lung studies rely on taxonomic profiling, and functional consequences of these
377 compositional shifts remain largely untested. Some common observations include an
378 overrepresentation of oral commensal bacteria (e.g. *Streptococcus*, *Neisseria*, *Prevotella*) in TB
379 sputum samples, likely due to increased transtracheal migration or impaired clearance (22). In
380 some studies, People with TB had higher abundance of gram-negative opportunists like
381 *Pseudomonas* and *Acinetobacter* in sputum, especially in those with lung cavitation or more
382 severe disease (possibly reflecting colonization of damaged airways). On the other hand, at least
383 one study found no significant difference in overall diversity or community composition between
384 TB and control sputum microbiota (7).

385
386 The multicenter analysis by Sala et al. (2020) concluded that there was no consistent TB-specific
387 lung microbiome signature across different populations (9). They observed that each patient's
388 sputum microbiota was highly individualized and influenced by geography and HIV status more
389 than by TB.

390
391 Intriguingly, one cross-sectional study noted an inverse relationship between *Streptococcus* and
392 certain anaerobes in sputum: people with TB whose sputum was dominated by *Streptococcus*
393 had lower overall diversity, whereas those with more anaerobic genera (like *Selenomonas*,
394 *Fusobacterium*) had higher diversity (22). This suggests that a balance between different
395 microbial groups (perhaps influenced by oxygen levels or inflammation in lesions) might shape
396 the lung microbiome diversity in TB.

397
398 Another observation is that in people with TB co-infected with HIV, the pulmonary microbiome
399 can include a substantial viral component – *Torqueteno* virus and *Epstein-Barr* virus (EBV) were
400 found to sometimes dominate the DNA in sputum of TB/HIV patients (22). This raises the question
401 of whether such shifts in the pulmonary virome and broader microbiome could contribute to the
402 increased risk of TB observed in people with HIV, beyond the effects of immune depletion alone.

403
404 These findings suggest that several reported pulmonary associations may reflect confounding by
405 host and contextual factors rather than TB disease per se, reinforcing the need for harmonized
406 protocols and carefully matched comparator groups. Differences in comparator groups across
407 studies—particularly the use of unmatched community controls versus household contacts or
408 alternative respiratory disease controls—likely further contribute to the observed lack of
409 reproducible pulmonary microbiome signatures.

410
411 **Functionally**, most lung microbiome studies have been taxonomic due to low biomass limiting
412 metagenomic sequencing, which is costly. It remains unclear if the TB lung dysbiosis (to the extent
413 it exists) has functional consequences for *Mtb* growth or host immunity in the lung, or if it is largely
414 bystander (36). Some hypothesize that loss of beneficial commensals in airways could reduce
415 colonization resistance against pathogens, potentially paving the way for secondary infections or
416 exacerbating inflammation (37).

417
418 By contrast, the **intestinal microbiome** in TB has shown more consistent patterns of disruption.
419 Numerous studies from different countries (China, India, Africa, etc.) report that gut microbial

420 diversity is reduced in active TB (38). One meta-analysis described a TB-associated gut
421 “dysbiosis signature” characterized by depletion of key SCFA-producing families (such as
422 *Ruminococcaceae* and *Lachnospiraceae*) and enrichment of taxa that can be pro-inflammatory
423 or opportunistic (such as *Enterococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Candida* in the mycobiome) (5). For
424 example, an early Chinese study found people with TB had lower relative abundance of
425 *Bifidobacterium* and *Prevotella* but higher *Clostridium* and *Enterobacteriaceae*, with several
426 inflammation-related functional pathways upregulated in microbiome predictive analysis (38).
427 Similarly, a Ghanaian study in 2023 noted that all people with TB (with or without diabetes or HIV)
428 shared a core dysbiosis: increased *Escherichia/Shigella*, *Streptococcus*, *Enterococcus* (potential
429 pathogens) and decreased beneficial butyrate-producers (4).

430
431 The presence of *Akkermansia* (a mucin-degrading genus often linked to gut barrier integrity) was
432 also found to be reduced in some TB cohorts, which might have implications for gut permeability
433 and systemic inflammation (39). Gut dysbiosis in TB is not only a consequence of the disease but
434 is exacerbated by TB treatment. Anti-TB therapy causes a rapid drop in commensal *Firmicutes*
435 (like *Faecalibacterium* and *Roseburia*) and often a bloom in *Bacteroides* and other taxa that resist
436 the drug cocktail (4). Hu *et al.* (2019) observed that within one week of starting HRZE therapy ,
437 *Firmicutes* abundance plummeted while certain *Bacteroides* OTUs and *Erysipelotrichaceae*
438 spiked, leading to a marked shift in community structure (10). Over the course of TB treatment,
439 some recovery of diversity can occur after the intensive phase, but many patients have a
440 persistently altered gut microbiota even at treatment completion (10). Mouse models mirror this:
441 conventional mice treated with TB drugs showed lasting depletion of gut microbes, and
442 interestingly, dysbiosis was more severe with certain drug combinations (39).

443
444 **Functionally**, the gut microbiome of people with TB has been linked to changes in metabolic
445 outputs – for instance, lower production of SCFA like butyrate (due to loss of producers) and
446 possibly altered tryptophan metabolism that could affect immune regulation (5). There is emerging
447 evidence that these gut microbiome changes have systemic effects: a study integrating gut
448 microbiome data with blood immune profiles found that the abundance of *Clostridiales* (clusters
449 IV and XIVa) in people with TB correlated with a normalization of peripheral inflammatory markers
450 during treatment (6). In other words, as TB treatment progressed, patients whose gut microbiota
451 regained beneficial *Clostridia* saw a stronger resolution of inflammation, independent of pathogen
452 clearance. This points toward a gut-immune interaction in TB, where gut microbiome composition
453 can influence systemic immune tone (the concept of the gut-lung axis), or alternatively reflect a
454 shared underlying cause (like malnutrition or ART in PWH) affecting the gut and lung microbiotas
455 and host immunity.

456 In summary, both pulmonary and intestinal microbiomes in TB show dysbiosis, though gut
457 changes are more consistent across studies. The “gut–lung axis” proposes that loss of SCFA-
458 producing gut microbes can trigger aberrant lung immune responses, influencing TB progression
459 (14). Conversely, TB infection and inflammation may alter gut ecology via systemic effects,
460 creating a bidirectional relationship. Mendelian randomization suggests the gut microbiome can
461 causally influence TB risk (12), potentially explaining differences in susceptibility beyond
462 established risk factors.

463 **Composition vs. Function: Multi-Omics Approaches**

464 Most early TB-microbiome studies have focused on taxonomic composition (e.g. which bacteria
465 increase or decrease in TB) using 16S rRNA gene sequencing. While informative, this approach
466 has inherent limitations. Microbiome function can diverge from composition – different microbial
467 communities may carry out similar functions (functional redundancy), and conversely, similar
468 community compositions can have different metabolic outputs depending on gene expression and
469 environmental context. In the context of TB, a purely compositional view might tell us, for example,
470 that people with TB have less *Prevotella* and more *Enterococcus* in their gut. However, it does
471 not tell us what that means for the host: Are SCFA levels reduced? Is there accumulation of pro-
472 inflammatory metabolites? Are microbial genes for vitamin K or vitamin B synthesis lost? Such
473 functional insights are critical for understanding how microbiome changes might influence TB
474 disease (or vice versa). Therefore, we are increasingly adopting multi-omics approaches –
475 integrating metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, metabolomics, and even host transcriptomics or
476 proteomics – to go beyond simple community profiling (40).

477
478 A multi-omics strategy in TB microbiome research might involve: sequencing the metagenome of
479 patient samples (to catalog microbial genes, including those for metabolic pathways or antibiotic
480 resistance), performing metatranscriptomics (RNA sequencing of microbiota to see which genes
481 are actively expressed), and conducting metabolomic analyses of patient blood, stool, or sputum
482 (to measure concentrations of microbial metabolites). These data layers can then be correlated
483 with host data such as cytokine profiles or clinical outcomes. **Figure 3** depicts a general pipeline
484 for such an integrative analysis. By combining data, one can identify not just “who is there” but
485 “what are they doing” and “how it affects the host.”

486
487 One example of a multi-omics insight comes from the integrative study by Wipperman et al.
488 (2021). In that work, researchers collected fecal samples, sputum, and blood from people with TB
489 during treatment and applied 16S sequencing for microbiome, conventional assays for Mtb
490 burden, and RNA-seq for host blood transcriptomes. Using machine learning, they found that
491 changes in the gut microbiome (specifically, increases in Clostridial families and decreases in
492 Proteobacteria) were independently associated with changes in the host peripheral immune
493 transcriptome remained associated with peripheral immune transcriptomic changes after
494 accounting for pathogen clearance, although residual confounding (e.g., diet, comorbidities)
495 cannot be excluded in observational human data (6). In other words, as patients got better, certain
496 gut microbes rebounded and correlated with reduced systemic inflammation. This suggests a
497 functional link: metabolites from those gut microbes could be modulating the immune response
498 to TB treatment. Notably, most longitudinal studies—including those linking microbiome recovery
499 to immune normalization—end follow-up at or before treatment completion, leaving the durability
500 of these associations and their relevance to relapse risk or post-TB lung disease largely unknown.

501
502 Complementing this, Naidoo et al. analyzed oral, sputum, and stool microbiota together with host
503 blood transcriptomes in untreated people with presumptive TB. They identified TB-specific
504 microbial relationships, including enrichment of stool anaerobes such as *Erysipelotrichaceae* and
505 *Blautia*, which correlated with host pro-inflammatory pathways (e.g., death receptor and

506 inflammasome signaling), thereby supporting a role of the gut microbiota in shaping TB-
507 associated immune responses even before therapy (41). Such conclusions could not be reached
508 from microbiome or host data alone; it was the integration that allowed the authors to propose
509 that “the response to therapy may be a combined effect of pathogen killing and microbiome-driven
510 immunomodulation”.

511
512 Another area where multi-omics is illuminating is in identifying microbial metabolites or pathways
513 that might influence TB. For instance, metabolomic profiles of people with TB have revealed
514 alterations in tryptophan and bile acid metabolites that could be traced back to microbiome
515 changes (42). Some gut bacteria produce indole derivatives that modulate the immune system; a
516 decrease in such bacteria in TB might lead to lower levels of these immunoregulatory molecules,
517 potentially affecting lung granuloma formation. Interestingly, one of these metabolites—indole-3-
518 propionic acid—not only regulates host inflammation but also directly inhibits *M. tuberculosis* by
519 targeting its tryptophan biosynthesis pathway, highlighting a dual host- and pathogen-directed
520 role for microbiome-derived indoles(43).

521
522 Such functional links are typically monitored by integrating metabolomic profiling of host samples
523 with metagenomic and immunological data, enabling correlations between microbial taxa, their
524 metabolic outputs, and host immune responses. Multi-omics analysis can link the dots—for
525 example, a reduced abundance of *Indolepropionibacter* in the gut metagenome could result in
526 lower concentrations of indolepropionic acid in the blood metabolome, which in turn may be
527 associated with heightened inflammation in the host transcriptome. Indeed, an emerging
528 hypothesis is that SCFAs produced by gut microbes (like butyrate) could suppress inflammation
529 and thus suppress TB-specific immune response. In mouse models, antibiotics that disrupt the gut
530 microbiota reduce macrophage-inducible C-type lectin (Mincle)-dependent activation of lung
531 dendritic cells, leading to weaker Th1/Th17 responses and higher *M. tuberculosis* burden.
532 Remarkably, these immune defects—and the increased susceptibility—can be reversed either by
533 stimulating Mincle with the agonist trehalose-6,6'-dibehenate or by supplementing with
534 *Lactobacillus* (44). This kind of mechanistic insight requires combining microbiome data with
535 immunological readouts (a form of cross-omics integration).

536
537 From a technological standpoint, advances in sequencing and computational biology now make
538 it feasible to perform such integrated analyses. Metagenomic sequencing can detect not only
539 bacteria but also viruses and fungi in TB patient samples – this is important since people with TB
540 often have perturbations in fungal (mycobiome) and viral communities as well (22). For example,
541 TB gut dysbiosis includes fungal overgrowth (e.g. *Candida* spp.) in some patients (5);
542 metagenomics or internal transcribed spacer (ITS) sequencing can capture these changes.
543 Metatranscriptomics can determine if *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* itself is active in the
544 microbiome community context – one study identified Mtb RNA transcripts in sputum microbiome
545 data, providing clues about Mtb physiology in patients alongside the commensal activity (45).
546 Furthermore, shotgun metagenomics allows assembly of genomes of uncultured organisms that
547 may play roles in TB (for instance, gut bacteria that metabolize TB drugs or modify host
548 metabolites). Multi-omics approaches have identified microbial genes associated with drug
549 metabolism; e.g., certain gut microbes harbor β -glucuronidase enzymes that can reactivate toxic

550 TB drug metabolites in the gut (46) potentially contributing to drug-induced liver injury (47). By
551 sequencing stool metagenomes of people with TB with vs. without liver toxicity, one study found
552 differences in these functional genes (39) – information that 16S alone would have missed.

553
554 To manage the complexity of multi-omics data, new computational pipelines (such as the gNOMO
555 of MIXOMICS tool for host–microbiome multi-omics integration (48,49) and network analysis
556 methods are being employed. These can construct host-microbe interaction networks, identify co-
557 occurring patterns, and pinpoint candidate “hub” metabolites or genes that link microbiome and
558 host responses.

559
560 In summary, moving from composition to function via multi-omics is critical in TB microbiome
561 research. It will help us to:

- 562 • Determine which microbial changes have functional importance (for example, loss of a
563 microbe that produces an anti-mycobacterial compound is more significant than loss of
564 one that does not).
- 565 • Identify microbial metabolites or gene pathways that interact with the host during TB.
- 566 • Discover potential biomarkers of disease or treatment response that are metabolite-based
567 (which might be more practical clinically than sequencing every patient’s microbiome).
- 568 • Understand the mechanistic of how microbiome alterations might affect TB immunity or
569 drug response.

570
571 Recent studies integrating multi-omics are already yielding richer hypotheses – such as the idea
572 that restoring certain gut microbial functions could enhance TB treatment response (6). However,
573 these approaches also come with challenges: increased cost, analytic complexity, and the need
574 for interdisciplinary expertise (microbiology, immunology, systems biology). Despite these
575 challenges, the consensus in the field is that a multi-omics lens is needed to fully grasp the TB-
576 microbiome interplay (40). As such, we are beginning to see a paradigm shift from simple case-
577 control 16S surveys to longitudinal, multi-layered studies that can inform not just *if* the microbiome
578 is different in TB, but *how* and *so what*.

579

580 **Potential Clinical Applications**

581 Understanding the microbiome’s role in TB offers tangible opportunities to improve care. **Figure**
582 **4**, illustrates how gut microbiota can sustain Mtb infection via SCFA-mediated Treg activation and
583 granuloma stability, whereas dysbiosis—driven by factors like LPS translocation and cytokine
584 imbalance—can promote progression to active disease. Reliable microbiome patterns or
585 metabolites linked to TB risk, progression, or treatment outcomes could serve as biomarkers or
586 therapeutic targets. If causality is confirmed (e.g. protective commensals), microbiome-based
587 interventions such as probiotics or dietary modulation could complement standard therapy. This
588 section explores three main clinical applications: biomarkers for diagnosis and prognosis,
589 microbiome predictors of treatment response or adverse effects, and targeted therapies to
590 improve outcomes or reduce toxicity.

591 **Microbiome biomarkers for TB diagnosis and risk stratification**

592 Microbiome composition or metabolite profiles could complement TB diagnosis and risk
593 assessment. Unlike conventional tests that detect the pathogen, microbiome biomarkers would
594 use the host's microbial "fingerprint" as an indirect indicator. Distinct gut profiles could enable
595 stool-based screening, though differences between TB infection (TBI) and TB disease remain
596 inconsistent (9). A multicenter lung study found no robust pulmonary TB signature (9), but
597 machine learning on sputum data achieved moderate discrimination from other lung diseases
598 (50).

599 It is important to distinguish between two potential applications: one is the direct detection of Mtb
600 reads or transcripts in metagenomic or metatranscriptomic datasets, which would serve as a
601 pathogen-specific diagnostic; the other is the identification of TB-associated microbial or
602 metabolite signatures (e.g., shifts in taxa or metabolites) that reflect host–microbiome interactions
603 rather than the presence of Mtb itself. Blood-derived microbial products, such as small RNAs
604 from *M. tuberculosis* or other microbiota (51), and serum metabolites—including SCFAs,
605 tryptophan catabolites, and lipids—are under investigation (52,53). Baseline microbiota may also
606 predict TB risk: Mendelian randomization links higher *Bacteroides* and lower *Bacillales* with
607 susceptibility (12), supporting potential for microbiome-based risk stratification and targeted
608 preventive or supportive interventions in high-risk or dysbiotic TB subgroups.

609 **Prognostic indicators and treatment response**

610 Microbiome profiling may help predict TB treatment response or relapse risk. Treatment is
611 lengthy, and patients vary in culture conversion time, relapse rates, and side effects. Early
612 identification of those at risk could guide management. In Wipperman *et al.*, gut microbiome
613 recovery paralleled immune normalization (6), suggesting microbiome monitoring as a surrogate
614 for progress. For example, a stool profile after 1 month might reveal a "resilient" versus "collapsed"
615 microbiota, the latter linked to poor health or persistent inflammation. Persistent dysbiosis after
616 therapy—such as loss of beneficial immunomodulatory microbes—may also raise relapse risk. A
617 cross-sectional Chinese study found recurrent TB cases had higher *Haemophilus* and
618 *Streptococcus* in sputum than new cases (50), hinting at a link between microbiome features and
619 chronicity. If validated, microbiome or metabolite biomarkers could inform TB management—for
620 instance, a low "microbiome health index" prompting closer follow-up or targeted adjunctive
621 therapies. An additional hypothesis, put forward by Scriba and colleagues (54), is that anti-TB
622 treatment may also deplete commensal NTMs that contribute to maintaining immune
623 responsiveness to Mtb, raising the possibility that therapy itself could inadvertently influence
624 susceptibility to future TB exposures. Extending microbiome follow-up beyond the standard 6-
625 month treatment course represents a major unmet need, particularly to understand long-term
626 immune recovery, relapse susceptibility, and post-TB lung disease.

627 **Microbiome-targeted adjunct therapies**

628 Perhaps the most promising application is microbiome modulation to improve TB outcomes
629 through probiotics, prebiotics, dietary interventions, or fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT).

630 Evidence from human and animal studies suggests that enhancing beneficial commensals could
631 boost anti-TB immunity, while preventing their loss during treatment may accelerate recovery and
632 reduce side effects. Approaches successful in other conditions, such as probiotics for antibiotic-
633 associated diarrhea or FMT for *Clostridioides difficile* colitis, could be adapted to TB (55). Small
634 trials in people with TB have shown that *Lactobacillus* or *Bifidobacterium* supplementation may
635 decrease systemic inflammation and reduce gastrointestinal symptoms (56).

636 Addressing TB-associated vitamin B deficiencies via probiotics or fermented foods is another
637 option. Preventing drug-induced liver injury (DILI) is a key target: certain gut bacteria can
638 metabolize isoniazid into hepatotoxins, and patients who developed DILI showed lower
639 *Phascolarctobacterium* and *Akkermansia*, and higher *Bacteroides* and *Enterococcus* (39).
640 Patients with DILI had lower baseline *Phascolarctobacterium* and *Akkermansia* (SCFA and
641 mucin-degraders) and higher *Bacteroides* and *Enterococcus*, suggesting a more pro-
642 inflammatory gut milieu (39). These differences were present within 2–3 weeks of therapy. This
643 raises the possibility that probiotic or dietary measures could prevent DILI – e.g. adding butyrate-
644 producing bacteria or their substrates to maintain intestinal integrity and reduce translocation of
645 inflammatory microbial products to the liver (42). Some groups have proposed administering
646 probiotics alongside TB drugs to decrease the incidence of hepatotoxicity and antibiotic-
647 associated diarrhea (57). These insights support a “microbiome stewardship” approach—
648 supporting or restoring gut ecology during and after TB therapy—to enhance cure rates, reduce
649 toxicity, and potentially limit post-TB lung damage.

650 Any microbiome-targeted intervention for TB requires caution. In immunocompromised patients,
651 such as those with HIV, live probiotics may pose infection risk at very low CD4 counts, and some
652 strains could metabolize TB drugs like isoniazid or rifampicin, warranting careful selection. Still,
653 potential benefits include faster recovery, fewer side effects, better quality of life, and possibly
654 reduced relapse if protective immunity is supported. Precision medicine could tailor interventions:
655 patients with severe dysbiosis may need intensive probiotic regimens, while those with preserved
656 microbiota might not. Randomized trials are needed to test whether restoring gut microbes via
657 probiotics or FMT reduces inflammation or toxicity (55). Early steps include studies combining
658 BCG vaccination with neonatal microbiome profiles to explore probiotic “adjuvants.”

659 Beyond interventions, microbiome insights could inform public health: integrating nutritional
660 support if diet proves key, or screening high-risk populations for predisposing microbiome traits.
661 Notably, the RATIONS cluster-randomised trial in India showed that providing food rations and
662 micronutrients to household contacts reduced incident TB by ~40–50% over two years (58);
663 embedding stool microbiome and metabolomic readouts in such large biosocial trials could help
664 explain differential benefit via diet–microbiome–immunity pathways and guide targeted scale-up.
665 Although not yet routine in TB care, the microbiome holds promise for diagnosis, prognosis, and
666 adjunctive therapy, reflecting a shift “beyond bacilli” toward viewing human microbial ecology as
667 both tool and target (57).

668

669 **Challenges and Future Directions**

670 The integration of microbiome research into the TB field, while promising, comes with numerous
671 challenges that must be addressed. In this section, we outline key challenges and propose future
672 research directions to advance our understanding of the TB-microbiome relationship and to
673 eventually translate findings into clinical benefit. Major areas of focus include: resolving
674 inconsistencies across studies through standardization, strengthening causal inference,
675 expanding research to under-studied facets (e.g. mycobiome, pediatric populations) and
676 designing interventional studies. **Table 3** summarizes the main barriers currently limiting the
677 translation of TB–microbiome research into clinical benefit, and outlines practical, evidence-
678 informed solutions.

679 ***Standardization and methodological rigor***

681 As highlighted, a major challenge is the heterogeneity in methods and populations across studies,
682 which contributes to inconsistent results. Future research should prioritize standardized protocols
683 for sample collection, DNA/RNA extraction, and sequencing when feasible. Efforts like the NIH’s
684 Human Microbiome Project have shown the value of standardizing methods to compare results
685 across sites – a similar approach in TB could enable meta-analyses that identify truly robust
686 microbiome signals. Developing guidelines for TB microbiome studies (e.g. how to handle low-
687 biomass lung samples, recommended confounder data to collect (13) would help new studies
688 avoid past pitfalls.

689 Additionally, making datasets (including comprehensive metadata) publicly available for re-
690 analysis can allow us to apply uniform bioinformatic pipelines and directly compare cohorts. On
691 the analysis side, more sophisticated statistical techniques should be employed to adjust for
692 confounders (e.g. multivariate models, batch effect corrections, inclusion of random effects for
693 household or cohort). As an example, one might include diet score (59), BMI, HIV status, and
694 antibiotic history as covariates in any analysis linking microbiome features to TB – something not
695 uniformly done in older studies. Embracing multi-omics also presents a standardization challenge:
696 different -omics data have different noise characteristics and it’s crucial to use robust methods for
697 data integration to avoid spurious correlations. Harmonizing how studies report their results
698 (perhaps adopting the STORMS reporting guidelines proposed for microbiome studies in disease
699 (60) will facilitate concise and complete reporting in microbiome studies).

701 ***Causal inference and mechanistic studies***

702 Most human TB–microbiome studies are observational, identifying associations but not causation.
703 Stronger study designs are needed to determine whether microbiome changes influence
704 susceptibility to TB or are a consequence of the disease. Longitudinal studies, such as tracking
705 latent TB cohorts, could reveal if baseline microbiota predict progression. Interventional models—
706 antibiotic-treated, germ-free, or fecal transplant in mice—show that microbiota depletion worsens
707 TB outcomes (55). Already, mice treated with antibiotics to deplete gut microbiota show worse TB
708 outcomes (55), supporting a causal protective role. “Humanized” mice colonized with TB patient
709 vs. healthy donor microbiota could test transmissible susceptibility. In humans, probiotic or dietary

710 trials could assess impacts on immunity and outcomes, where faster sputum clearance or reduced
711 inflammation would imply causality. Mendelian randomization (57), offers another tool, using
712 genetic proxies for microbiome traits. Mechanistic work should dissect pathways, e.g., how
713 butyrate-producing bacteria enhance macrophage Mtb-killing. Multi-omics can identify candidate
714 metabolites for in vitro testing with immune cells. This shift from correlation to experimental
715 validation will provide the rationale for microbiome-targeted therapies.

716 ***Expanding scope: mycobiome, virome and beyond 16S***

717 Future TB microbiome research should broaden its scope beyond bacteria. The gut mycobiome
718 (fungal community) and virome (viruses, including bacteriophages) are parts of the mucosal
719 ecosystem that have been relatively neglected. Initial studies suggest the mycobiome is perturbed
720 in TB: for example, in a comparative cross-sectional study, people with TB were found to have a
721 perturbed gut mycobiome marked by significantly reduced fungal diversity and increased
722 abundance of *Candida* and *Saccharomyces* species compared to healthy controls (5,61). Fungal
723 products (such as β -glucans) can influence immune responses, so changes in fungi might also
724 matter for TB immunity. Likewise, phages that infect gut bacteria could impact which bacteria
725 thrive under TB treatment. Going forward, integrated analyses of bacteria, fungi, and viruses
726 (possible with metagenomic sequencing) will give a more complete picture of the microbiome
727 changes in TB.

728 ***Special populations (pediatric TB, extrapulmonary TB, asymptomatic TB)***

729 Most studies have focused on adult pulmonary TB. Pediatric TB is an important context: children's
730 gut microbiome is still developing, highly sensitive to diet, and potentially more vulnerable to long-
731 lasting disruption from antibiotics. Malnutrition and TB often coexist in children; it would be
732 valuable to study how nutritional rehabilitation and microbiome restoration interplay in pediatric
733 TB outcomes (8). Similarly, extrapulmonary TB (like TB meningitis or intestinal TB) might have
734 unique microbiome considerations. For example, recent studies characterizing the site-of-disease
735 microbiome in tuberculous lymphadenitis and pericarditis have shown that these niches are not
736 microbially homogeneous, but rather display distinct microbial "lymphotypes" or pericardial
737 profiles associated with HIV status, disease severity, and enrichment of pathways such as short-
738 chain fatty acid metabolism (62,63).

739
740 Intestinal TB could also be directly influenced by gut microbiota composition, given its
741 gastrointestinal localization; indeed, one study suggested that gut microbiome profiles could help
742 distinguish intestinal TB from other inflammatory bowel conditions (64). Going forward, including
743 these special cases will broaden our understanding and perhaps reveal stronger microbiome
744 signals—for instance, the gut microbiome might be even more relevant in intestinal TB
745 pathogenesis.

746 ***Therapeutic development and clinical trials***

747 To move towards clinical translation, interventional trials are needed to test microbiome-based
748 strategies. This is a clear future direction: small Phase II trials could investigate whether adding

749 a certain probiotic to standard TB therapy improves patient weight gain or reduces gut
750 inflammation (measured by fecal calprotectin, for instance). If successful, larger trials could
751 measure hard outcomes like sputum conversion rates or incidence of hepatotoxicity. There is also
752 interest in whether post-TB lung disease (the chronic lung impairment many TB survivors have)
753 can be ameliorated by microbiome modulation – perhaps an anti-inflammatory microbiome could
754 reduce fibrosis or chronic obstructive changes. Trials to address that would need long-term follow-
755 up. Another futuristic idea is microbiome-derived pharmaceuticals: identifying a metabolite from
756 a commensal that has anti-TB properties or immunomodulatory effects and developing it as a
757 drug. For example, if indolepropionic acid (a microbial metabolite) proves to boost host TB
758 defenses, one could test giving it as a supplement (43).

759

760 These strategies align with the growing global focus on host-directed therapies for TB (65,65),
761 and the microbiome makes a strong candidate for inclusion in this pipeline, given its ability to
762 modulate immunity, inflammation, and drug metabolism. Such translational leaps will require a
763 pipeline from discovery to preclinical testing to clinical trials.

764 ***Collaboration and interdisciplinary research***

765 The complexity of TB-microbiome interactions means that future progress will rely on
766 collaboration across disciplines – microbiologists, TB clinicians, immunologists, bioinformaticians,
767 and even social scientists (for diet/lifestyle data) need to work together. Large cohort studies like
768 Stool4TB (61,66) are incorporating microbiome analyses alongside detailed clinical phenotyping;
769 similar integrative projects should be encouraged. International collaborations could enable
770 studying how the microbiome-TB link might differ in high TB burden settings (with more
771 environmental mycobacteria exposure, for instance) versus low burden settings. There’s also a
772 need for capacity building in low-income countries to perform microbiome research, as these are
773 the regions where TB is most prevalent and local factors will influence the microbiome. Future
774 studies should be designed with community engagement, particularly when diet or nutritional
775 interventions are considered, to ensure feasibility and cultural acceptability.

776 ***Knowledge gaps***

777 Some of the key questions going forward are summarized in [Figure 5](#). Addressing these will likely
778 require novel study designs, such as adaptive trials that can test multiple interventions, or systems
779 biology models that integrate multi-omics data to predict outcomes, which can then be
780 experimentally validated.

781

782 In summary, the future of TB-microbiome research is bright but challenging. By tackling
783 confounders, standardizing methodologies, and focusing on mechanistic and translational
784 studies, the field can progress from observational association to evidence-based applications. As
785 one *Lancet Respiratory Medicine* review aptly stated, the goal is to reach a stage where
786 microbiome insights can be “defining the clinical research agenda” for TB and be harnessed for
787 patient benefit (20). This will require patience and rigor, but the potential rewards – improved TB
788 diagnostics, adjunct therapies to shorten treatment or reduce suffering, and perhaps even
789 preventative strategies leveraging the microbiome – are well worth the concerted effort.

790 **Conclusion**

791 A decade of research has firmly established that TB does not occur in isolation but within the
792 complex ecosystem of the human microbiome. While disruptions to the gut and lung microbiota
793 in TB are increasingly documented, interpreting these changes demands rigorous attention to
794 confounders, methodological standardization, and a shift from descriptive to functional analyses.
795 This review highlights the need to move beyond compositional surveys and adopt multi-omics
796 strategies to identify mechanistic links between microbiome alterations and TB pathogenesis or
797 treatment outcomes.

798 The translational potential of microbiome science in TB is now tangible: microbiome-derived
799 biomarkers could enhance diagnosis or risk stratification; monitoring microbiome recovery may
800 predict treatment success or relapse; and adjunctive therapies—nutritional, probiotic, or
801 applications will require methodologically harmonized, causally informative, and context-specific
802 research across diverse TB-endemic settings.

803 The field stands at a turning point: from observational association to mechanistic understanding
804 and clinical innovation. To accelerate progress, we must foster interdisciplinary collaboration,
805 build capacity in high-burden regions, and establish international standards for TB-microbiome
806 research. With rigorous science and coordinated effort, integrating microbiome insights into TB
807 care could transform both our biological understanding and clinical management of this global
808 disease. Ultimately, recognizing the host as an ecosystem—not just a battleground between
809 pathogen and immunity—opens new frontiers in precision TB medicine.

810

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824 No primary data were generated. The review is based on analysis and interpretation of
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826

827 **GENERATIVE AI DISCLOSURE**

828 The authors used AI-assisted tools (ChatGPT, OpenAI) to support language editing and
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830

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839 **REFERENCES**

- 840 1. Global Tuberculosis Report 2024. 1st ed. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2024. 1 p.
- 841 2. Wood MR, Yu EA, Mehta S. The Human Microbiome in the Fight Against Tuberculosis. *Am*
842 *Soc Trop Med Hyg.* 2017 June 7;96(6):1274–84.
- 843 3. Hu Y, Cheng M, Liu B, Dong J, Sun L, Yang J, et al. Metagenomic analysis of the lung
844 microbiome in pulmonary tuberculosis - a pilot study. *Emerg Microbes Infect.* 2020
845 Jan;9(1):1444–52.
- 846 4. Morgan PA, Parbie PK, Ntiamoah DO, Boadu AA, Asare P, Lamptey INK, et al. Gut
847 microbiome variation in pulmonary TB patients with diabetes or HIV comorbidities. *Front*
848 *Microbiomes.* 2023 Mar 15;2:1123064.
- 849 5. Maji A, Misra R, Dhakan DB, Gupta V, Mahato NK, Saxena R, et al. Gut microbiome
850 contributes to impairment of immunity in pulmonary tuberculosis patients by alteration of
851 butyrate and propionate producers. *Environ Microbiol.* 2018 Jan;20(1):402–19.
- 852 6. Wipperman MF, Bhattarai SK, Vorkas CK, Maringati VS, Taur Y, Mathurin L, et al.
853 Gastrointestinal microbiota composition predicts peripheral inflammatory state during
854 treatment of human tuberculosis. *Nat Commun.* 2021 Feb 18;12(1):1141.
- 855 7. Cheung MK, Lam WY, Fung WYW, Law PTW, Au CH, Nong W, et al. Sputum Microbiota in
856 Tuberculosis as Revealed by 16S rRNA Pyrosequencing. Bereswill S, editor. *PLoS ONE.*
857 2013 Jan 24;8(1):e54574.
- 858 8. Zhou H, Pei Y, Xie Q, Nie W, Liu X, Xia H, et al. Diagnosis and insight into the unique lung
859 microbiota of pediatric pulmonary tuberculosis patients by bronchoalveolar lavage using
860 metagenomic next-generation sequencing. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol.* 2024 Dec
861 19;14:1492881.
- 862 9. Sala C, Benjak A, Goletti D, Banu S, Mazza-Stadler J, Jatton K, et al. Multicenter analysis of
863 sputum microbiota in tuberculosis patients. Wilkinson KA, editor. *PLOS ONE.* 2020 Oct
864 12;15(10):e0240250.
- 865 10. Hu Y, Yang Q, Liu B, Dong J, Sun L, Zhu Y, et al. Gut microbiota associated with pulmonary
866 tuberculosis and dysbiosis caused by anti-tuberculosis drugs. *J Infect.* 2019 Apr;78(4):317–
867 22.
- 868 11. Namasivayam S, Maiga M, Yuan W, Thovarai V, Costa DL, Mittereder LR, et al.
869 Longitudinal profiling reveals a persistent intestinal dysbiosis triggered by conventional anti-
870 tuberculosis therapy. *Microbiome.* 2017 July 7;5(1):71.
- 871 12. Yuan Z, Kang Y, Mo C, Huang S, Qin F, Zhang J, et al. Causal relationship between gut
872 microbiota and tuberculosis: a bidirectional two-sample Mendelian randomization analysis.
873 *Respir Res.* 2024 Jan 4;25(1):16.
- 874 13. Vujkovic-Cvijin I, Sklar J, Jiang L, Natarajan L, Knight R, Belkaid Y. Host variables confound
875 gut microbiota studies of human disease. *Nature.* 2020 Nov;587(7834):448–54.

- 876 14. Mori G, Morrison M, Blumenthal A. Microbiome-immune interactions in tuberculosis. Hiller
877 NL, editor. *PLOS Pathog.* 2021 Apr 15;17(4):e1009377.
- 878 15. Burr AHP, Bhattacharjee A, Hand TW. Nutritional Modulation of the Microbiome and
879 Immune Response. *J Immunol.* 2020 Sept 15;205(6):1479–87.
- 880 16. Kau AL, Ahern PP, Griffin NW, Goodman AL, Gordon JI. Human nutrition, the gut
881 microbiome and the immune system. *Nature.* 2011 June 16;474(7351):327–36.
- 882 17. Son P. Impact of Dietary Interventions on Gut Microbiota Composition and Immune Health.
883 *J Nutr Diet.* 7(2).
- 884 18. Musuenge BB, Poda GG, Chen PC. Nutritional Status of Patients with Tuberculosis and
885 Associated Factors in the Health Centre Region of Burkina Faso. *Nutrients.* 2020 Aug
886 21;12(9):2540.
- 887 19. Miyoshi J, Rao MC, Chang EB. Navigating the Human Gut Microbiome: Pathway to
888 Success from Lessons Learned. *Gastroenterology.* 2020 Dec;159(6):2019–24.
- 889 20. Naidoo CC, Nyawo GR, Wu BG, Walzl G, Warren RM, Segal LN, et al. The microbiome and
890 tuberculosis: state of the art, potential applications, and defining the clinical research
891 agenda. *Lancet Respir Med.* 2019 Oct;7(10):892–906.
- 892 21. Liu N, Liu J, Zheng B, Zeng X, Ye Z, Huang X, et al. Gut microbiota affects sensitivity to
893 immune-mediated isoniazid-induced liver injury. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2023
894 Apr;160:114400.
- 895 22. Ticlla MR, Hella J, Hiza H, Sasamalo M, Mhimbira F, Rutaihua LK, et al. The Sputum
896 Microbiome in Pulmonary Tuberculosis and Its Association With Disease Manifestations: A
897 Cross-Sectional Study. *Front Microbiol.* 2021 Aug 20;12:633396.
- 898 23. Vujkovic-Cvijin I, Somsouk M. HIV and the Gut Microbiota: Composition, Consequences,
899 and Avenues for Amelioration. *Curr HIV/AIDS Rep.* 2019 June;16(3):204–13.
- 900 24. Serrano-Villar S, Rojo D, Martínez-Martínez M, Deusch S, Vázquez-Castellanos JF,
901 Bargiela R, et al. Gut Bacteria Metabolism Impacts Immune Recovery in HIV-infected
902 Individuals. *EBioMedicine.* 2016;8:203–16.
- 903 25. Beck JM, Schloss PD, Venkataraman A, Twigg H, Jablonski KA, Bushman FD, et al.
904 Multicenter Comparison of Lung and Oral Microbiomes of HIV-infected and HIV-uninfected
905 Individuals. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2015 Dec 1;192(11):1335–44.
- 906 26. Wang Y, Guo A, Zou Y, Mu W, Zhang S, Shi Z, et al. Interaction between tissue-dwelling
907 helminth and the gut microbiota drives mucosal immunoregulation. *Npj Biofilms
908 Microbiomes.* 2023 June 24;9(1):43.
- 909 27. Natukunda A, Zirimenya L, Nassuuna J, Nkurunungi G, Cose S, Elliott AM, et al. The effect
910 of helminth infection on vaccine responses in humans and animal models: A systematic
911 review and meta-analysis. *Parasite Immunol.* 2022 Sept;44(9):e12939.

- 912 28. Sailani MR, Metwally AA, Zhou W, Rose SMSF, Ahadi S, Contrepolis K, et al. Deep
913 longitudinal multiomics profiling reveals two biological seasonal patterns in California. *Nat*
914 *Commun.* 2020 Oct 1;11(1):4933.
- 915 29. Wingfield T, Schumacher SG, Sandhu G, Tovar MA, Zevallos K, Baldwin MR, et al. The
916 Seasonality of Tuberculosis, Sunlight, Vitamin D, and Household Crowding. *J Infect Dis.*
917 2014 Sept 1;210(5):774–83.
- 918 30. Botero LE, Delgado-Serrano L, Cepeda ML, Bustos JR, Anzola JM, Del Portillo P, et al.
919 Respiratory tract clinical sample selection for microbiota analysis in patients with pulmonary
920 tuberculosis. *Microbiome.* 2014 Dec;2(1):29.
- 921 31. Sinha R, Abnet CC, White O, Knight R, Huttenhower C. The microbiome quality control
922 project: baseline study design and future directions. *Genome Biol.* 2015 Dec;16(1):276.
- 923 32. Ren W, Zhong Y, Ding Y, Wu Y, Xu X, Zhou P. Mismatches in 16S rRNA Gene Primers: An
924 Area Worth Further Exploring. *Front Microbiol.* 2022 June 13;13:888803.
- 925 33. Lin H, Peddada SD. Analysis of compositions of microbiomes with bias correction. *Nat*
926 *Commun.* 2020 July 14;11(1):3514.
- 927 34. Rohart F, Gautier B, Singh A, Lê Cao KA. mixOmics: An R package for 'omics feature
928 selection and multiple data integration. Schneidman D, editor. *PLOS Comput Biol.* 2017 Nov
929 3;13(11):e1005752.
- 930 35. Mirzayi C, Renson A, Genomic Standards Consortium, Massive Analysis and Quality
931 Control Society, Furlanello C, Sansone SA, et al. Reporting guidelines for human
932 microbiome research: the STORMS checklist. *Nat Med.* 2021 Nov;27(11):1885–92.
- 933 36. Segal LN, Clemente JC, Li Y, Ruan C, Cao J, Danckers M, et al. Anaerobic Bacterial
934 Fermentation Products Increase Tuberculosis Risk in Antiretroviral-Drug-Treated HIV
935 Patients. *Cell Host Microbe.* 2017 Apr;21(4):530-537.e4.
- 936 37. Yang L, Li N, Yi X, Wang Z. The translational potential of the lung microbiome as a
937 biomarker and a therapeutic target for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Interdiscip*
938 *Med.* 2023 Oct;1(4):e20230023.
- 939 38. Ding X, Zhou J, Chai Y, Yan Z, Liu X, Dong Y, et al. A metagenomic study of the gut
940 microbiome in PTB'S disease. *Microbes Infect.* 2022 Mar;24(2):104893.
- 941 39. Pei S, Yang L, Gao H, Liu Y, Lu J, Dai EH, et al. The association between the gut
942 microbiome and antituberculosis drug-induced liver injury. *Front Pharmacol.* 2025 Mar
943 10;16:1512815.
- 944 40. Otchere ID, Aboagye SY, Arthur PK, Asante-Poku A. Viewpoint of multi-omics potential in
945 tuberculosis research: identifying biomarkers for biomanufacturing of efficient control tools.
946 *Front Trop Dis.* 2024 July 31;5:1443248.
- 947 41. Naidoo CC, Nyawo GR, Sulaiman I, Wu BG, Turner CT, Bu K, et al. Anaerobe-enriched gut
948 microbiota predicts pro-inflammatory responses in pulmonary tuberculosis. *EBioMedicine.*
949 2021 May;67:103374.

- 950 42. Li G, Hou Y, Zhang C, Zhou X, Bao F, Yang Y, et al. Interplay Between Drug-Induced Liver
951 Injury and Gut Microbiota: A Comprehensive Overview. *Cell Mol Gastroenterol Hepatol*.
952 2024;18(3):101355.
- 953 43. Negatu DA, Yamada Y, Xi Y, Go ML, Zimmerman M, Ganapathy U, et al. Gut Microbiota
954 Metabolite Indole Propionic Acid Targets Tryptophan Biosynthesis in *Mycobacterium*
955 *tuberculosis*. Jackson M, Kaufmann SHE, editors. *mBio*. 2019 Apr 30;10(2):e02781-18.
- 956 44. Negi S, Pahari S, Bashir H, Agrewala JN. Gut Microbiota Regulates Mincle Mediated
957 Activation of Lung Dendritic Cells to Protect Against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Front*
958 *Immunol*. 2019 May 28;10:1142.
- 959 45. Shah T, Shah Z, Baloch Z, Cui X. The role of microbiota in respiratory health and diseases,
960 particularly in tuberculosis. *Biomed Pharmacother*. 2021 Nov;143:112108.
- 961 46. Biernat KA, Pellock SJ, Bhatt AP, Bivins MM, Walton WG, Tran BNT, et al. Structure,
962 function, and inhibition of drug reactivating human gut microbial β -glucuronidases. *Sci Rep*.
963 2019 Jan 29;9(1):825.
- 964 47. Wang P, Jia Y, Wu R, Chen Z, Yan R. Human gut bacterial β -glucuronidase inhibition: An
965 emerging approach to manage medication therapy. *Biochem Pharmacol*. 2021
966 Aug;190:114566.
- 967 48. Chetty A, Blekhman R. Multi-omic approaches for host-microbiome data integration. *Gut*
968 *Microbes*. 2024 Dec 31;16(1):2297860.
- 969 49. Welham Z, Déjean S, Lê Cao KA. Multivariate Analysis with the R Package mixOmics. In:
970 Burger T, editor. *Statistical Analysis of Proteomic Data* [Internet]. New York, NY: Springer
971 US; 2023 [cited 2025 July 2]. p. 333–59. (Methods in Molecular Biology; vol. 2426).
972 Available from: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-1-0716-1967-4_15
- 973 50. Kamaruddin M, Massi MN. Sputum microbiota in normal human, new TB patients, and
974 recurrent tuberculosis patients as identified by 16SrRNA sequencing [Internet]. *Open*
975 *Science Framework*; 2020 [cited 2025 July 2]. Available from: <https://osf.io/pqnk9>
- 976 51. Gu W, Huang Z, Fan Y, Li T, Yu X, Chen Z, et al. Peripheral blood microbiome signature
977 and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*-derived rsRNA as diagnostic biomarkers for tuberculosis in
978 human. *J Transl Med*. 2025 Feb 19;23(1):204.
- 979 52. Tien NTN, Yen NTH, Phat NK, Anh NK, Thu NQ, Dinh Hoa V, et al. Circulating Lipids as
980 Biomarkers for Diagnosis of Tuberculosis: A Multi-cohort, Multi-omics Data Integration
981 Analysis [Internet]. *Respiratory Medicine*; 2024 [cited 2025 July 2]. Available from:
982 <http://medrxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2024.08.06.24311536>
- 983 53. Wang MG, Wu SQ, Zhang MM, He JQ. Urine metabolomics and microbiome analyses
984 reveal the mechanism of anti-tuberculosis drug-induced liver injury, as assessed for
985 causality using the updated RUCAM: A prospective study. *Front Immunol*. 2022 Nov
986 22;13:1002126.

- 987 54. Dutt TS, Karger BR, Fox A, Youssef N, Dadhwal R, Ali MZ, et al. Mucosal exposure to non-
988 tuberculous mycobacteria elicits B cell-mediated immunity against pulmonary tuberculosis.
989 Cell Rep. 2022 Dec;41(11):111783.
- 990 55. Zhuo Q, Zhang X, Zhang K, Chen C, Huang Z, Xu Y. The gut and lung microbiota in
991 pulmonary tuberculosis: susceptibility, function, and new insights into treatment. Expert Rev
992 Anti Infect Ther. 2023 Dec 2;21(12):1355–64.
- 993 56. Lin S, Zhao S, Liu J, Zhang J, Zhang C, Hao H, et al. Efficacy of proprietary *Lactobacillus*
994 *casei* for anti-tuberculosis associated gastrointestinal adverse reactions in adult patients: a
995 randomized, open-label, dose–response trial. Food Funct. 2020;11(1):370–7.
- 996 57. Su Y, Lu N, Li Q, Wen H, Zhang XQ, Zhang M. Gut Microbiota and Drug-Related Liver
997 Injury: Challenges and Perspectives. Wu J, editor. Adv Gut Microbiome Res. 2023 Jan
998 19;2023:1–9.
- 999 58. Bhargava A, Bhargava M, Meher A, Benedetti A, Velayutham B, Sai Teja G, et al. Nutritional
1000 supplementation to prevent tuberculosis incidence in household contacts of patients with
1001 pulmonary tuberculosis in India (RATIONS): a field-based, open-label, cluster-randomised,
1002 controlled trial. The Lancet. 2023 Aug;402(10402):627–40.
- 1003 59. Kase BE, Liese AD, Zhang J, Murphy EA, Zhao L, Steck SE. The Development and
1004 Evaluation of a Literature-Based Dietary Index for Gut Microbiota. Nutrients. 2024 Apr
1005 3;16(7):1045.
- 1006 60. Mirzayi C, Renson A, Genomic Standards Consortium, Massive Analysis and Quality
1007 Control Society, Furlanello C, Sansone SA, et al. Reporting guidelines for human
1008 microbiome research: the STORMS checklist. Nat Med. 2021 Nov;27(11):1885–92.
- 1009 61. Han M, Wang X, Zhang J, Su L, Ishaq HM, Li D, et al. Gut bacterial and fungal dysbiosis in
1010 tuberculosis patients. BMC Microbiol. 2024 Apr 25;24(1):141.
- 1011 62. Nyawo G, Naidoo CC, Wu BG, Kwok B, Clemente JC, Li Y, et al. Bad company? The
1012 pericardium microbiome in people investigated for tuberculous pericarditis in an HIV-
1013 prevalent setting. Microbes Infect. 2025;27(3):105434.
- 1014 63. Nyawo GR, Naidoo CC, Wu B, Sulaiman I, Clemente JC, Li Y, et al. More than
1015 *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*: site-of-disease microbial communities, and their functional and
1016 clinical profiles in tuberculous lymphadenitis. Thorax. 2023 Mar;78(3):297–308.
- 1017 64. Kashyap PC, Chia N, Nelson H, Segal E, Elinav E. Microbiome at the Frontier of
1018 Personalized Medicine. Mayo Clin Proc. 2017 Dec;92(12):1855–64.
- 1019 65. Cubillos-Angulo JM, Nogueira BMF, Arriaga MB, Barreto-Duarte B, Araújo-Pereira M,
1020 Fernandes CD, et al. Host-directed therapies in pulmonary tuberculosis: Updates on anti-
1021 inflammatory drugs. Front Med. 2022 Sept 23;9:970408.
- 1022 66. Consortium S. (Stool4TB). 2025 [cited 2025 Aug 19]. Evaluating a new stool-based qPCR
1023 for diagnosis of tuberculosis in children and people living with HIV. Available from:
1024 <https://www.stool4tb.org>

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1026 **TABLES**

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Table 1. Key Confounding Factors in TB-Microbiome Studies		
Confounding Factor	Impact on Microbiome and Considerations in TB Studies	Ref
Diet and Nutrition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diet shapes gut microbiota composition • People with TB often malnourished or with distinct diets. • Differences in fiber intake and food diversity can drive microbiome changes unrelated to TB. • Controls must be matched for diet or nutritional status to avoid confounding. • Malnutrition itself alters immunity and microbiota, potentially influencing TB outcomes. 	Morgan et al., 2023
Antibiotic Use (incl. TB drugs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Past or concurrent antibiotics can drastically alter microbiota. • TB therapy (prolonged multi-drug regimen) causes loss of commensals and overgrowth of others. • Microbiome samples taken after treatment may reflect drug effects rather than TB. • It is necessary to sample before treatment or include untreated TB and control groups. 	Hu et al., 2019; Sala et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2017
Co-morbidities (HIV, Diabetes, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conditions like HIV and diabetes independently affect the microbiome and immune response. • HIV co-infection in TB is associated with distinct sputum microbiota (e.g. higher viral load in lung secretions). • Diabetic People with TB show different gut microbiome shifts than non-diabetic People with TB. • These factors must be stratified or adjusted for; otherwise microbiome differences may actually be due to the co-morbidity. 	Morgan et al., 2023; Ticlla et al., 2021
Geography & Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional and environmental differences (urban vs. rural, sanitation, climate) strongly influence baseline microbiome. • Multi-country studies found no universal TB microbiome signature, only location-specific patterns. • TB prevalence often correlates with low- and middle-income settings which have different microbiomes from high-income controls. • Using local community or household controls is important. • Socioeconomic factors (housing, pollution) also act as confounders. 	Morgan et al., 2023; Sala et al., 2020
Sampling Method/Site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences in sample type between People with TB and controls can confound results. • Control group selection (community vs household vs sick controls) strongly influences observed microbiome differences. • For lung studies, TB cases produce sputum while controls may give throat swabs – oral flora in swabs can differ from sputum. • Sputum passes through the mouth, picking up oral bacteria; thus some “lung” differences might just reflect oral contamination. • Consistent sampling (e.g. using comparable upper airway samples in both groups) or careful interpretation is needed. 	Botero et al., 2014

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similarly, stool vs. mucosal biopsies in gut studies can yield different community profiles. 	
Low Biomass & Contamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pulmonary samples in TB are low biomass and therefore highly susceptible to reagent and environmental contamination, making stringent negative controls and decontamination pipelines essential for valid inference. • DNA from laboratory reagents or the environment can skew results if not controlled, especially in studies that do not include negative controls. • Meticulous lab practice (blank controls, decontamination) and analytical filtering are required to ensure true TB-associated microbes are identified. 	Naidoo et al., 2019
Sequencing /Analysis Differences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variations in DNA extraction kits, 16S rRNA primers, sequencing platform, and bioinformatics can introduce biases. • If cases and controls are processed in different batches or with different protocols, observed microbiome differences may be artefactual (e.g., a given primer might under-detect <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> in cases, or a bioinformatic pipeline might misclassify taxa in one group). • Standardizing methods and including batch as a covariate in analysis help mitigate this confounder. 	Mori et al., 2021

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Domain	Pulmonary Microbiome (TB vs. Healthy)	Intestinal Microbiome (TB vs. Healthy)
Diversity	Often reduced; low-diversity communities dominated by oral commensals.	Consistently reduced α -diversity; loss of beneficial fermenters.
Taxonomic Shifts	No universal TB signature – high inter-person variability and strong confounding by geography, HIV status, sampling site/type, and contamination control. \uparrow <i>Streptococcus</i> , <i>Pseudomonas</i> , <i>Haemophilus</i> ; \downarrow obligate anaerobes. Oral contamination common. Some TB cases resemble controls.	Convergence on \downarrow SCFA producers (<i>Faecalibacterium</i> , <i>Roseburia</i>) and \uparrow <i>Escherichia/Shigella</i> , <i>Enterococcus</i> . <i>Prevotella</i> often depleted. Taxa-level effects vary by undernutrition, comorbidities, antibiotics, and geography.
Functional Changes	Limited data. Oral flora may obscure true lung microbiota signals.	\downarrow vitamin biosynthesis; \uparrow metabolism of host-derived compounds (e.g., bile acids, propionate). SCFA balance may shift and affect immune regulation.
Treatment Effects	Mixed: some studies report \downarrow diversity post-treatment; others show minimal impact. Changes subtle and confounded by oral microbiome.	Rapid and marked dysbiosis within days of therapy. \downarrow <i>Firmicutes</i> , \uparrow <i>Bacteroides/Proteobacteria</i> . Incomplete recovery post-treatment. Long-term (>6–12 months) outcomes largely uncharacterized.
Comorbidities	TB/HIV patients had sputum dominated by commensal viruses (Torque teno, EBV) not seen in HIV-/TB, indicating co-infection alters the lung microbiome.	Risk factors for TB (HIV, malnutrition, diabetes, geography, age) affect the gut microbiome.
Representative Studies	Cheung et al, Plos ONE 2013; Ticlla et al., 2021; Sala et al., 2020	Ding et al., 2022; Maji et al., 2018; Morgan et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2019; Pei et al., 2025

Challenge	Description	Proposed Solutions
High inter-study variability	Differences in results due to inconsistent sample collection, sequencing methods, and populations	Adopt standardized protocols for sampling, DNA/RNA extraction, and analysis; follow reporting guidelines (e.g., MIRROR, STORMS); share datasets for harmonized re-analysis
Confounding factors	Patient diet, antibiotics, co-infections (HIV, diabetes), geography, and sampling site all confound microbiome signals	Match cases/controls on key variables (e.g., diet, HIV status), use stratified analysis, collect detailed metadata, and apply multivariate adjustment
Causality unclear	Most human studies are cross-sectional and cannot distinguish cause from consequence	Use longitudinal cohort designs (e.g., household contact follow-up), launch clinical trials (e.g., probiotics), and Mendelian randomization analyses to infer causality
Low biomass & contamination (especially in lung samples)	Risk of detecting reagent or environmental contaminants rather than true microbes in sputum/BAL	Include negative/blank controls, perform decontamination filtering, and interpret low-biomass results cautiously
Limited functional data	16S rRNA sequencing gives taxonomic profiles, but lacks insight into microbial function	Integrate multi-omics (metagenomics, metabolomics, transcriptomics), and link microbial profiles to host immunity and metabolite outputs
Understudied microbial domains	Fungal (mycobiome) and viral (virome) communities are rarely studied, despite relevance in TB and antibiotic use	Include ITS and viral metagenomic sequencing; analyze fungal and viral dynamics alongside bacterial profiles
Neglected populations or TB forms	Pediatric TB, extrapulmonary TB, pregnant women with HIV, and high-risk populations (e.g. malnourished) are underrepresented	Design studies focused on children, intestinal TB, and high-burden settings; include community and nutritional context
Lack of translational studies	Few trials test if microbiome modulation improves TB outcomes or reduces toxicity	Launch randomized trials of microbiome-based adjunct therapies (e.g., probiotics, diet, FMT); explore post-TB microbiome recovery strategies
Fragmented research landscape	Siloed studies with limited data sharing or cross-disciplinary input	Promote collaborative consortia, build capacity in TB-endemic regions, and support interdisciplinary research (clinical, microbiome, immunology, systems biology)

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1033 **Figure 1. Overview of Confounders in Microbiome Research for TB.** These include: (1) Patient
 1034 characteristics, such as co-infections (e.g. HIV, helminths), comorbidities (e.g. diabetes), antibiotic
 1035 use, nutrition, and lifestyle; (2) Environmental and contextual factors, including geography,
 1036 sanitation, climate, and socioeconomic status; and (3) Methodological variables, encompassing
 1037 sample type, laboratory protocols, sequencing platforms, and study design. Some confounders (e.g.
 1038 HIV, diabetes, malnutrition, antibiotic use, and socioeconomic status) are particularly important
 1039 because they can influence both the microbiome and TB susceptibility or progression directly. These
 1040 dual-impact factors must be carefully accounted for to avoid spurious associations and ensure
 1041 accurate interpretation and reproducibility of results.

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1045 **Figure 2. Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) illustrating sources of confounding in microbiome-**
1046 **tuberculosis (TB) association studies.** DAG 1–3 depict distinct confounding domains: patient-
1047 level (DAG 1), environmental/contextual (DAG 2), and methodological (DAG 3). Each includes
1048 variables that may influence both the microbiome and TB outcomes, potentially biasing observed
1049 associations. DAG 4 integrates these domains into a unified causal framework. Node colors denote
1050 variable categories. Arrows indicate hypothesized causal relationships.

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From sample to mechanisms: a multi-omic framework for functional microbiome analyses in TB

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1053 **Figure 3. Integrated Multi-Omics and Experimental Validation Pipeline for TB-Microbiome**
 1054 **Research.** Microbiome studies in tuberculosis face methodological challenges, including sampling
 1055 variability, low biomass, and batch effects (left panel). To move beyond descriptive composition, a
 1056 multi-omics approach combines metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, metabolomics, and host omics
 1057 to uncover functional pathways linking microbiota to TB outcomes (center). These insights must be
 1058 tested through experimental validation, including mechanistic studies in animal models and host
 1059 immune assays (right). Together, this framework enables robust causal inference and supports the
 1060 discovery of translational applications, such as biomarkers or microbiome-based interventions.
 1061 Arrows do not imply causality unless supported by experimental validation

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1064 **Figure 4. Microbiome-driven modulation of host immunity in tuberculosis: pathways to**
 1065 **latency or active disease.** This figure illustrates two contrasting immunological outcomes in
 1066 tuberculosis—immune containment versus disease progression—driven by gut microbiome
 1067 composition and function. **Left panel (Latent TB):** A balanced and diverse gut microbiota supports
 1068 homeostatic immunity through the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), including butyrate
 1069 and propionate. These metabolites enhance regulatory T cell (Treg) function and IL-10 secretion
 1070 via G-protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) signaling, promote gut epithelial integrity, and prevent
 1071 microbial translocation. Commensal-driven modulation of Toll-like receptor (TLR) signaling
 1072 (TLR2/TLR4) ensures appropriate activation of IFN-γ and TNF-α responses, sustaining granuloma
 1073 formation and stability. These mechanisms collectively support containment of *Mycobacterium*
 1074 *tuberculosis* within granulomas, maintaining a latent infection state. **Right panel (Active TB):**
 1075 Microbiome dysbiosis—resulting from antibiotic exposure, HIV infection, or metabolic
 1076 comorbidities—alters SCFA-producing species (e.g., *Clostridia*, *Roseburia*, *Bacteroides fragilis*)
 1077 and increased abundance of potentially detrimental taxa (e.g., *Enterococcus*, *Escherichia*, *Shigella*,
 1078 *Enterobacteriaceae*). SCFA depletion weakens epithelial barrier integrity, facilitating translocation
 1079 of microbial products such as lipopolysaccharide (LPS) and elevating levels of LPS-binding protein
 1080 (LBP). This systemic microbial translocation contributes to dysregulated TLR signaling, cytokine
 1081 production toward an inflammatory profile (↑ IL-6, ↓ IL-10, ↓ IFN-γ), impairing macrophage
 1082 activation and granuloma integrity. The resulting immune dysregulation promotes breakdown of
 1083 granuloma structures and progression to active TB disease.

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Figure 5. Knowledge gaps and research priorities in TB–microbiome research.

Unanswered questions include: (i) identifying keystone microbial species or consortia that influence TB susceptibility or recovery; (ii) defining microbial metabolites that mediate host–microbiome crosstalk, such as short-chain fatty acids or tryptophan catabolites; (iii) clarifying the timing and persistence of microbiome perturbations, from early-life influences on TB risk to restoration after treatment; (iv) developing practical microbiome-based tools for clinical use, such as simplified metabolite indices or dried blood spot assays; and (v) characterizing how multidrug-resistant TB regimens reshape microbial communities and impact outcomes. Addressing these gaps will require adaptive clinical trials, systems biology and multi-omics integration, and experimental validation to move from observational associations to causal and translational insights.